

increased with increased nitrogen from 50 to 200 kg/ha.

October 1981, when most of the cultivars were in the boot or flowering stage, was unusually dry (total rainfall 22.7 mm), with a minimum temperature of 23.1°C, maximum temperature 41°C, 77% relative humidity, and 8.9 hours sunshine. The dry weather appears to have favored sheath rot. □

TABLE CONTINUED

Cultivars	Disease score ^a at different nitrogen levels			
	50 kg/ha	100 kg/ha	150 kg/ha	200 kg/ha
CR294-28-1, CR294-548-2	1	3	7	7
CR294-548-3, CR315-621	1	5	7	7
ET4141	3	5	5	7
Jaya, Ramkrishna	5	5	7	7
PR107	5	7	7	7
BG90-2	0	7	7	7
CR188-10	1	3	5	7

^a 1 = resistant, 3 = moderately resistant, 5 = moderately susceptible, 7 = susceptible.

Screening of rice varieties for resistance to ragged stunt disease

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Seeds of 47 rice varieties collected from southern and central China (Guangdong, Guang Xi, Hu Nan, Hu Bei, Jiang Xi, and Fu Jian Provinces) were sown in seedboxes. At the 3- to 4-leaf stage, 34 viruliferous brown planthopper adults were released on each plant and allowed to feed for 3 days. Seedlings were transplanted to the paddy field.

All test varieties were susceptible, except IR36 with an infection rate of 12.5% (see table). Highly susceptible Guang Lu Ai 4, Bai Zhen Long, Zhen Long 13, and Hong 410 were severely stunted. Tall varieties had no significant stunting at the early stage, but were severely stunted at later stages.

Some varieties first showed leaf twisting and later ragged leaf symptoms.

Varietal resistance to ragged stunt, Guangdong, China, 1980.

Variety	Inoculated (no.)	In-fected (no.)	In-fecton (%)	Variety	Inoculated (no.)	In-fected (no.)	In-fecton (%)
IR36	32	4	12.5	Gui Chao Ai	39	38	97.4
IR29	20	6	30.0	Bai Yi Wan 1	30	30	100
Yu Chi 231-8	30	15	50.0	Guang Lu Ai4	25	25	100
Guang Yu 73	28	21	75.0	Hong 408	35	35	100
76-116	29	22	75.9	Guang Er 104	18	18	100
PII 299	30	24	80.0	Bai Zhen Long	34	34	100
PII 292	27	23	85.2	IR206 1	12	12	100
78-804	18	16	88.9	IR26	34	34	100
75-89	29	26	89.7	Qiang Hong 35-2	22	22	100
Shan You 2	23	21	91.3	Quan Ye Bai	30	30	100
75013	24	22	91.7	22-3	29	29	100
PII 293	21	25	92.6	150	25	25	100
91228	29	27	93.1	Hong 410	25	25	100
7055	29	27	93.1	Zhan Long 13	29	29	100
Wu Dong 51	15	14	93.3	Yuan Feng Zao	28	28	100
Nong Ken 58	25	24	96.0	Zhu Bian Xuan	26	26	100
Si You 2	27	26	96.3	Cong Siu Qing	23	23	100
E-Wan 3	27	26	96.3	5450	30	30	100
73-151	28	27	96.4	5180	20	20	100
PII 298	29	28	96.6	Gan Nan Wan	30	30	100
Er Jiu Qing	30	29	96.7	15-5	30	30	100
Shan You 3	30	29	96.7	PII 291	29	29	100
PII 300	30	29	96.7	TN1	28	28	100
Xiang Ai Zao	31	30	96.8				

Others first showed ragged leaf symptoms and later leaf twisting. Still others first had vein-swelling symptoms. In

severely affected plants panicles did not exert. The plants became shorter and shorter and finally died. □

A note on rice blast in Tanzania

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Rice blast incited by *Pyricularia oryzae* is the most prevalent rice disease in Tanzania, but no empirical data on the extent of losses from it are available.

An experiment was conducted at Morogoro, central-eastern Tanzania, to determine the extent of loss caused by blast. Two rice cultivars — Kihogo Red (resistant to blast) and Faya Theresa (susceptible) — were planted in a split-

plot experiment with five replications under irrigation in February 1980. The cultivars were randomly allocated to the main plots. There was no artificial inoculation; the disease developed from natural inoculum. Fungicide treatment (spraying vs no spraying) was randomly allocated to the subplots to generate different disease levels. The fungicide benomyl (Benlate 50 WP) at 1 kg ai/ha was sprayed 6 times at 2-week intervals starting 46 days after planting. Control plots were sprayed with water. Disease severity was assessed four times and scored using the Standard Evaluation System for Rice.

Disease differences were highly significant between the resistant and susceptible cultivars, and between the sprayed and unsprayed plots of the susceptible Faya Theresa (see figure).

The rice was harvested in July 1980 then sun-dried, threshed, winnowed, and weighed (adjusted to 14% moisture content). Paddy yields per hectare and 1,000-paddy grain weight in the sprayed and unsprayed plants of the two cultivars are in the table. There was an 18% reduction in yield and an 11% reduction in 1,000-grain weight in Faya Theresa. Both reductions were highly significant. Disease by